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Ten new species of the genus *Thaumastocephalus* Poggi et al. 2001 (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) from Mount Biokovo and neighbouring mountains in Central Dinarides

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SUMMARY. Ten new species of *Thaumastocephalus*: *T. bartulovici* sp. n., *T. basarai* sp. n., *T. buljubasici* sp. n., *T. dryadalis* sp. n., *T. fortisi* sp. n., *T. inesae* sp. n., *T. nonveilleri* sp. n., *T. poggii* sp. n., *T. roglici* sp. n. and *T. visianii* sp. n., from Central Dinarides in Croatia, are described and illustrated. The morphology characters of new species are analysed, as well as their chorology and ecology preferences. A distribution maps of all known 18 species of *Thaumastocephalus* is given. Basic ecological data are presented. Distribution data expressed significantly high biodiversity of the genus *Thaumastocephalus* on Biokovo Mt., suggested that this mountain is the main centre of radiation of the genus.

KEY WORDS: Caves, Croatia, stenoendemic, taxonomy, troglobionts.

INTRODUCTION

The tribe Thaumastocephalini was established for the genus *Thaumastocephalus* Poggi, Nonveiller, Colla, Pavićević & Radja, 2001, an anophthalmous and cavernicolous pselaphine of very peculiar features discovered in Central Dalmatia, Croatia. It was placed in the super-tribe Batrisitae (Poggi et al., 2001). The genus remained monospecific for 18 years, until Hlaváč et al. (2019) described seven new species from Central Dinarides. *Thaumastocephalus* species can be distinguished from each other mainly by male dimorphic features, such as more or less modified profemora, protibiae and mesotibiae, and by the conformation of the aedeagus. However, females are morphologically quite uniform and lack unambiguous diag-

nostic characters. Recently, Jałoszyński et al. (2023) described a new genus and species of an epigeal pselaphine from Central Turkey, *Percussiopalpus inusitatus* Hlaváč & Jałoszyński, 2023, resembling enough *Thaumastocephalus* to be assigned to Thaumastocephalini, a tribe they transferred on this occasion from Batrisitae to Euplectitae.

In this article we describe further 10 new species of *Thaumastocephalus*: eight from Biokovo Mt., and two from neighbouring mountains, Mosor Mt. and Šibenik Mt., Central Dalmatia, Croatia.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens of the genus *Thaumastocephalus* were searched in caves by visual inspection of the cave walls, as well as by turning stones on the cave floor. Traps with attractants did not produce results. Specimens found were collected using appropriate gentle tweezers and inserted into terrain vials, with 70% ethanol. In laboratory, the ethanol was replaced, and the samples appropriately labelled.

During research, basic cave microclimate was measured: air temperature, substrate temperature, relative air humidity, optionally also content of CO₂ in air. Also cave habitats were recognized, according to National habitat classification of Republic of Croatia, ver. 5.0. published in Rulebook on the list of habitat types and habitat map and connected documents. According to the conditions in the finding micro localities, and specimens' activity, the found specimens were macro-photographed *in situ*, using several camera models, mostly CANON EOS 4000 with a close-up objective, and OLYMPUS MJU TOUGHT, several generations.

For the laboratory study of specimens, LEICA MZ 16 and WILD M 8 ZOOM stereomicroscope were used, as well as CARL ZEISS AXIOSCOPE 40 microscope. Measurements for specimens were performed for: total body length, head length, maximum width of head, antennal length, pronotum length, pronotum width, elytral length, elytral width.

Male genitalia were dissected, put in Caryophylli aetheroleum solution (Clove oil) for several hours, then mounted in Canada balsam, on plastic transparent slides, and pinned under the dry prepared specimens.

Thaumastocephalus species differ from each other mainly by male dimorphic features. Therefore, when more than one species of *Thaumastocephalus* were found in the same cave we preferred to not include the female specimens of that cave in the paratype series of the new species.

Collection depository is given for each specimen, with inventory number for the holotypes.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AL antennal length

BA Bosnia and Hercegovina

CDP private collection of Dragan Pavićević, Belgrade (Serbia)

EL elytral length (as linear distance measured along the suture from the elytral base to the apex)

EW maximum width of elytra

HL head length: measured from the anterior margin of the clypeus to the neck constriction

HR Croatia

HW maximum width of head

LT Locus typicus

masl metres above sea level

MHNG Muséum d'histoire naturelle, Geneva, Switzerland

NHGMV Natural-history Department of State Museum of Varaždin city (GMV) (Croatia)

NHMZ Natural-history Museum in Zagreb (Croatia)

PL pronotum length

PW maximum width of pronotum

RH Relative humidity of the air

ROC Roman Ozimec Collection, part of NHGMV (Croatia)

Ta Temperature of air

TL total body length: measured from the apex of mandibles to the apex of last tergite

Ts Temperature of substrate

TAXONOMY

Thaumastocephalus bartulovici sp. n. (Figs 1, 3A, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., G. Brela, Bartulovići, Špilja Drinova 2 cave, 525 masl, 08.11.2009, leg. R. Ozimec. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106601.

PARATYPES: 1 female, same data as holotype, leg. P. Rade; 1 female, same data as previous but collected 08.11.2008, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, same data as previous

but collected 18.05.2010, leg. H. Cvitanović; 1 female, same data as previous but collected 23.03.2003, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, same data but collected 03.07.2022, leg. R. Ozimec & I. Vuković; 2 males, 1 female, same data as previous but collected 3.11.2015, leg. H. Cvitanović; 1 male, Biokovo Mt., Pozjata špilja cave, 1460 masl, 26.10.2003, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, 1 female, Biokovo Mt., Zagvozd, Špilja u Gaju cave, 440 masl, 18.10.2002, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, same data as previous, but leg. B. Jalžić; 1 male, 1 female, Zagvozd, Ogradice, Pružina špilja cave, 519 masl, 15.10.2002, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, Biokovo Mt., Rastovac, Raputinova špilja cave, 352 masl, 24.11.2005, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 female, Biokovo Mt., Rastovac, Dedići, Špilja u Radinovićima cave, 310 masl, 25.10.2006, leg. R. Ozimec (Coll. CDP, MHNG, ROC).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.10 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.40 mm, HW 0.31 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.71 mm) long; scape 0.15/0.05; pedicel 0.08/0.04; antennomere III 0.05/0.03, IV 0.04/0.03, V 0.04/0.023, VI 0.04/0.03, VII 0.04/0.03, VIII

Fig. 1. *Thaumastocephalus bartulovici* sp. n. in Špilja Drinova 2 cave on 03.07.2022, photo R. Ozimec.

0.04/0.03, IX 0.04/0.04, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.15/0.09. Pronotum (PL 0.38 mm, PW 0.39 mm) nearly as long as wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.53 mm, EW 65 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.38/0.68 mm. Profemora not modified. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine obtuse. Aedeagus (Fig. 3A) 0.47 mm long, right paramere more robust than left one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with one robust and two slender asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. TL 2.10-2.20 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus bartulovici* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the right paramere more robust than left one, not constricted sub-basally, and with tip acutely angulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing one robust and two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora not modified, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a well-formed obtuse median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after Marin Bartulović (1940-2020), our friend and guide to the caves and pits in this part of Biokovo Mt.

Fig. 2. Špilja Drinova 2 cave Map, vertical and horizontal profile (after Tropea & Ozimec, 2020).

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from six speleological sites: Špilja Drinova 2 cave (Fig. 2), Pozjata špilja cave, Pružina špilja cave, Raputinova špilja cave, Špilja u Gaju cave, and Špilja u Radinovićima cave, the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY (After Tropea & Ozimec, 2020).

Basic data	Cave on 525 masl, depth -12.3 m, length 94.5 m, simple cave with a two cave chambers. Map on Fig. 2.
Microclimate	Ta = 12.2 °C; Ts = 11.8 °C; Tw = 10.5 °C; RH: 96-100%; CO ₂ = 2512-4525 ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	Scorpiones: <i>Euscorpium biokovensis</i> Tropea & Ozimec, 2020.
Other taxa in LT	Gastropoda: <i>Hypnophila</i> sp., <i>Spelaeoconcha</i> sp., <i>Vitrea</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Apfelbeckia</i> sp., <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Lithobius</i> sp., <i>Eupolybothrus</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Barusia</i> sp., <i>Meta</i> sp., <i>Nesticus</i> sp., <i>Histopona</i> sp., <i>Stalagtia</i> sp., <i>Sulcia</i> sp., <i>Tegenaria</i> sp., <i>Typhloniphia</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Cyphophthalmus</i> sp., <i>Nelima</i> sp., <i>Trogulus</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp., <i>Roncus</i> sp.; Diplura: <i>Stygiocampa</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Laemostenus</i> sp., <i>Neotrechus</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp., Orthoptera: <i>Dolichopoda</i> sp., <i>Grylломорpha</i> sp., <i>Troglophilus</i> sp.

***Thaumastocephalus basarai* sp. n.** (Figs 3B, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Supin, Jama za Supinom pit, 965 masl, 18.11.2005, leg. R. Ozimec. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106602.

PARATYPES: 1 female, same data as holotype (Coll. CDP).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.50 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.47 mm, HW 0.35 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.83 mm) long; scape 0.19/0.05; pedicel 0.10/0.05; antennomere III 0.05/0.05, IV 0.04/0.03, V 0.04/0.03, VI 0.04/0.03, VII 0.04/0.03, VIII 0.04/0.03, IX 0.04/0.04, X 0.05/0.04, XI 0.20/0.10. Pronotum (PL 0.45 mm, PW 0.42 mm) slightly longer than wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL

Fig. 3. Aedeagi, dorsal view. **A:** *T. bartulovici* sp. n.; **B:** *T. basarai* sp. n.; **C:** *T. buljubasici* sp. n.; **D:** *T. dryadalis* sp. n. Scale bar 0.1 mm.

0.58 mm, EW 72 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.38/0.72 mm. Profemora not modified. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine absent. Aedeagus (Fig. 3B) 0.45 mm long, left paramere more robust than right one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with one asymmetrical sclerite.

VARIABILITY. TL 2.40-2.50 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus basarai* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the left paramere more robust than right one, slight constricted in middle, possessing a subapical cylindrical process projecting medially, and with tip rounded; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing one slender sclerite; 3) the profemora not modified, and 4) the protibiae not modified.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after Damir Basara, speleologist from Karlovac and long-time cooperative associate researcher on Biokovo Mt./Biokovo Nature Park.

Fig. 4. Jama za Supinom pit, author D. Basara (after Ozimec, 2012).

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY (All after Ozimec, 2012).

Basic data	Cave on 965 masl, depth -82.3 m, length 372.2 m, extremely complex morphology, represents a knee shaped SO, with several floors. Map on Fig. 4.
Microclimate	Ta = 9.5-11.7 °C; Ts = 9.6-10.5 °C; Tw = 9.5 °C; RH: 96-100%; CO ₂ = 419-867 ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	No taxa previously described, only Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeobiocovica radici</i> nom. nud.
Other taxa in LT	Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeoconcha</i> sp.; <i>Zospeum</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Stalagtia herzegowensis</i> , <i>Typhloniphia reimoseri</i> , <i>Stygopholcus</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpiniscus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Biokoviella mauriesi</i> , <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp., <i>Macrochaetosoma troglomontanum biokovense</i> ; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Troglochthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Cyphophthalmus</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Diplura: <i>Plusiocampa (Stygocampa)</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Neotrechus dalmatinus dalmatinus</i> , <i>Speonesiotes narentinus narentinus</i> , <i>Laemostenus cavicola</i> ; Orthoptera: <i>Gryllomorpha dalmatina</i> , <i>Dolichopoda araneiformis</i> , <i>Troglophilus cavicola</i> .

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from the Jama za Supinom pit, on Biokovo Mt., Dalmatia, HR (Fig. 4), the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

***Thaumastocephalus buljubasici* sp. n.** (Figs 3C, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Župa, Matijaševa peć cave, 584 masl, 25.05.2004, leg. B. Jalžić. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106603.

PARATYPES: 1 male, same data as holotype but collected in 5.11.2015, leg. H. Cvitanović; 1 male, Biokovo Mt. Župa, Samogorska špilja cave, 717 masl, 25.05.2004, leg. J. Bedek (Coll. CDP).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.14 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.40 mm, HW 0.34 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless.

Antennae (AL 0.81 mm) long; scape 0.15/0.05; pedicel 0.08/0.04; antennomere III 0.04/0.03, IV 0.03/0.02, V 0.03/0.02, VI 0.03/0.02, VII 0.03/0.02, VIII 0.03/0.02, IX 0.03/0.03, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.15/0.08. Pronotum (PL 0.45 mm, PW 0.43 mm) slightly longer than wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.53 mm, EW 70 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.43/0.71 mm. Profemora with obtuse proximal thorn. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine obtuse. Aedeagus (Fig. 3C) 0.48 mm long, left paramere more robust than right one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with two asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. TL 1.82-2.47 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus buljubasici* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the left paramere more robust than right one, slightly constricted in middle, without subapical process, and with tip rounded; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora possessing a proximal thorn, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a well-formed obtuse median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after our friend Ivica Buljubašić who helped us many times with cave researches in Biokovo Mt., and supported us in many other ways.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY.

Basic data	Cave on 584 masl, depth m, length m, simple morphology. No map.
Microclimate	Ta = 6.1-10.5 °C; Ts = 5.8-10.0 °C; Tw = - °C; RH: 92-100%; CO ₂ = 668 ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	No taxa previously described.
Other taxa in LT	Gastropoda: <i>Semilimax</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Sulcia</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp., <i>Macrochaetosoma</i> sp., <i>Apfelbeckia</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp.; Scorpiones: <i>Euscorpius</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Nelima</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Bilobella</i> sp., <i>Orchesella</i> sp., <i>Tomocerus</i> sp.; Zygentoma: <i>Coletinia</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Neotrechus</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp.; Orthoptera: <i>Dolichopoda araneiformis</i> ; Lepidoptera: <i>Triphosa</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from 2 caves located very near from each other on Biokovo Mt., Dalmatia, HR, the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. Accord-

ing to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

Thaumastocephalus dryadalis sp. n. (Figs 3D, 5, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Tučepi, Jama pod stijenom kod Tučepske Vilenjače pit, 1214 masl, 19.05.2010, leg. R. Ozimec & P. Rade. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106604.

PARATYPES: 2 males, 6 females, same data as holotype; 1 male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Tučepi, Špilja Tučepska Vilenjača cave (Fig. 6), 1181 masl, 18.11.2011, leg. H. Cvitanović (Coll. ROC, CDP, MHNG).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 1.90 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.42 mm, HW 0.30 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless.

Fig. 5. *Thaumastocephalus dryadalis* sp. n. in Jama pod stijenom kod Tučepske Vilenjače pit, on 19.05.2010, photo R. Ozimec.

Antennae (AL 0.71 mm) long; scape 0.20/0.05; pedicel 0.06/0.04; antennomere III 0.05/0.03, IV 0.03/0.03, V 0.03/0.03, VI 0.03/0.03, VII 0.03/0.03, VIII 0.03/0.03, IX 0.03/0.03, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.20/0.08. Pronotum (PL 0.50 mm, PW 0.40 mm) longer than wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.55 mm, EW 70 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.38/0.63 mm. Profemora with proximal thorn. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine minute, obtuse. Aedeagus (Fig. 3D) 0.45 mm long, left paramere more robust than right one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with two asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. TL 1.90 – 2.00 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus dryadalis* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the left paramere more robust than right one, gently and evenly widening toward apex, without subapical process, and with tip acutely angulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora with a proximal thorn, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a minute obtuse median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. From the Latin word *dryadalis* – dryad or elf, in Croatian – šumska vila, with reference to the Tučepska Vilenjača cave, what mean- Dryad house of Tučepi village.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY (For both finding caves).

Basic data	Pit on 1214 masl, depth 7 m, length 2 m, very simple morphology. No map.
Microclimate	Ta = 8.4 °C; Ts = 7.8 °C; Tw = - °C; RH: 100%; CO ₂ = 1094 ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310. NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglolitic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	In type locality no taxa previously described. Tučepska Vilenjača is LT for one species: Araneae: <i>Mesostalita comottii</i> (Gasparo, 1999).
Other taxa in LT	Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeoconcha</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Eupolybothrus</i> sp., <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp., <i>Apfelbeckia</i> sp.; Acari: <i>Rhagidia</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Harpactes</i> sp., <i>Stalagtia</i> sp., <i>Stygopholcus</i> sp., <i>Typhlonypbia</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Cyphophthalmus</i> sp., <i>Nelima</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Troglopedetes</i> sp., <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Laemostenus</i> sp., <i>Neotrechus</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp., <i>Leptomeson</i> sp.; Orthoptera: <i>Troglophilus</i> sp., Lepidoptera: <i>Triphosa</i> sp., <i>Apopestes</i> sp., <i>Pyrois</i> sp., <i>Alucita</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from Jama pod stijenom kod Tučepske Vilenjače pit, and very near and more famous Tučepska Vilenjača cave (Fig. 6) on Biokovo Mt., Dalmatia, HR, the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

Fig. 6. Špilja Tučepska Vilenjača cave, vertical and horizontal profile (after Jalžić et al., 2022).

Thaumastocephalus fortisi sp. n. (Fig. 7A, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., G. Igrane, Jama iznad Saranača pit, 735 masl, 25.05.2004, leg. R. Ozimec. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106605

PARATYPES: 1 female, same data as holotype; 1 female, same data as holotype but collected in 15.11.2010, leg. J. Bedek; 1 female, same data as previous but collected in 22.06.2007, leg. J. Bedek (Coll. CDP, MHNG).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.19 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.40 mm, HW 0.33 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.66 mm) long; scape 0.18/0.06; pedicel 0.07/0.04; antennomere III 0.04/0.03, IV 0.03/0.03, V 0.03/0.03, VI 0.04/0.03, VII 0.04/0.03, VIII 0.04/0.04, IX 0.04/0.05, X 0.04/0.05, XI 0.15/0.10. Pronotum (PL 0.36 mm, PW 0.38 mm)

Fig. 7. Aedeagi, dorsal view. A, *Thaumastocephalus fortisi* sp. n.; B, *Thaumastocephalus nonveilleri* sp. n. Scale bar 0.1 mm.

slightly wider than long, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.50 mm, EW 68 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.33/0.68 mm. Profemora not modified. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine absent. Aedeagus (Fig. 7A) 0.54 mm long, right paramere more robust than left one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with two asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. 2.19 -2.20 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus fortisi* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the right paramere more robust than left one, gently and evenly widening toward apex, without subapical process, and with tip acutely angulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora not modified, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, lacking a median spine.

Fig. 8. Jama iznad Saranača pit, vertical and horizontal profile (after Jalžić et al., 2010).

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after Alberto Fortis (1741-1803), Italian theologian, naturalist, travel writer and monk. In his book *Viaggio in Dalmazia* (Journey to Dalmatia) (1774), he described his researches on Biokovo Mt., motivated by deep pits on Biokovo Mt., which were claimed to be the source of the famous strong endemic wind – bura.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY.

Basic data	Small knee-shaped pit, -20 m deep.
Microclimate	Ta = 10.5-11.1 °C; Ts = 12.2 °C; Tw = - °C; RH: 96%; CO ₂ = -ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	Isopoda: <i>Strouhaloniscellus biokovoensis</i> Bedek & Taiti, 2009.
Other taxa in LT	Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeoconcha</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp., <i>Trichoniscus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Apfelbeckia</i> sp., <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp., <i>Macrochaetosoma</i> sp., <i>Glomeris</i> sp., <i>Dyocerasoma</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Pholcus</i> sp., <i>Lepthyphantes</i> sp., <i>Stalagtia</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Nelima</i> sp., <i>Cyphophthalmus</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp.; Scorpiones: <i>Euscorpium</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Tomocerus</i> sp., <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Neotrechus</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp.; Orthoptera: <i>Troglophilus</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from Jama ispod Saranača pit (Fig. 8) on east edge of Biokovo Mt., Dalmatia, HR, the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

***Thaumastocephalus nonveilleri* sp. n.** (Figs 7B, 9, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Bast, Kukor špilja cave, 510 masl, 26.03.2003, leg. R. Ozimec. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106607

PARATYPES: 1 male, same data as holotype, but collected in 23.06.2007, leg. J. Bedek; 1 female, same data as previous but collected in 25.03.2004, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, 1 female, same data as previous, but collected in 26.03.2008, leg. R. Ozimec (Coll. CDP, MHNG, ROC).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.13 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.38 mm, HW 0.34 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.70 mm) long; scape 0.15/0.05; pedicel 0.08/0.04; antennomere III

Fig. 9. *Thaumastocephalus nonveillieri* sp. n. (photo by G. Cuccodoro).

0.05/0.03, IV 0.04/0.03, V 0.04/0.03, VI 0.04/0.03, VII 0.04/0.03, VIII 0.04/0.03, IX 0.03/0.03, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.15/0.09. Pronotum (PL 0.45 mm, PW 0.45 mm) as long as wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.58 mm, EW 69 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.39/0.70 mm. Profemora with obtuse proximal thorn. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine absent, or forming at most a low swelling. Aedeagus (Fig. 7B) 0.46 mm long, left paramere more robust than right one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with two asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. TL 2,13 – 2.22 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus nonveillieri* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the left paramere more robust than right one, gently and evenly narrowed toward apex, without subapical process, with tip acutely angulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora possessing a proximal thorn; 4) Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal

half, lacking a median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after our colleague and friend, Prof. Dr Guido Nonveiller (1913-2002), the world specialist of mutillid wasps, as well as of the cavernicolous and endogean Coleoptera fauna of Balkan.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY.

Basic data	Cave, 279 m long, with a vertical difference of 35 m. Map in Fig. 10.
Microclimate	Ta = 12.6-16.1 °C; Ts = 11.9-15.0 °C; Tw = - °C; RH: 98-100 %; CO ₂ = 500-600 ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	Coleoptera: <i>Biokovobythus radici</i> Pavićević & Ozimec, 2013.
Other taxa in LT	Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus balthasari</i> (Frankenberger, 1937), <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp., <i>Troglocyphoniscus absoloni</i> Strouhal, 1939, <i>Oroniscus dalmaticus</i> Strouhal, 1937, <i>Echinarmadillidium fruzgalii</i> (Verhoeff, 1900); Chilopoda: <i>Eupolybothrus</i> sp., <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Apfelbeckia insculpta</i> (L. Koch, 1867), <i>Brachydesmus subterraneus</i> Heller, 1857, <i>Trachysphaera</i> sp., <i>Typhloiulus</i> sp.; Acari: <i>Speleothrombium</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Harpactes</i> sp., <i>Sulcia</i> sp., <i>Nesticus</i> sp., <i>Lepthyphantes</i> sp., <i>Pholcus</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Nelima troglodytes</i> Roewer, 1910, <i>Trogulus setosissimus</i> Roewer, 1940; Collembola: <i>Pseudosinella</i> sp., <i>Heteromurus nitidus</i> Templeton, 1835, <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp., <i>Tomocerus terrestralis</i> Stach, 1922; Orthoptera: <i>Troglophilus ovuliformis</i> Karny, 1907, <i>Dolichopoda araneiformis</i> Burmeister, 1838, <i>Gryllomorpha dalmatina</i> (Ocskay, 1832).

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from Kukor špilja cave near Bast (Fig. 10), the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

Thaumastocephalus inesae sp. n. (Figs 11, 13A, 18)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Šibenik Mt., Kozica, Antunovići, Velika špilja cave, 427 masl, 02.07.2022, leg. I. Vuković & R. Ozimec. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106606.

PARATYPES: 1 male, same data as holotype; 1 female, same data, but collected in 23.03.2004, leg. R. Ozimec (Coll. CDP).

Fig. 10. Kukor špilja cave, vertical and horizontal profile (after Pavićević & Ozimec, 2013).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.30 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.40 mm, HW 0.31 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.84 mm) long; scape 0.18/0.04; pedicel 0.08/0.04; antennomere III 0.05/0.03, IV 0.04/0.02, V 0.04/0.03, VI 0.04/0.03, VII 0.04/0.03, VIII 0.04/0.03, IX 0.04/0.04, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.20/0.10. Pronotum (PL 0.45 mm, PW 0.40 mm) longer than wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.55 mm, EW 72 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.40/0.70 mm. Profemora with obtuse proximal thorn. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine minute. Aedeagus (Fig. 11A) 0.47 mm long, right paramere more robust than left one, both with three preapical setae; internal sac with one robust and two slender asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. TL 1.97-2.30 mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus inesae* sp. n. can be distinguished

from its congeners by: 1) the right paramere more robust than left one, strongly constricted sub-basally, without subapical process, with tip acutely angulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac possessing one robust and two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora possessing a proximal thorn, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a minute median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after our colleague Ines Vuković, biologist from Ploče town, and cooperative associate researcher on Biokovo Mt./Biokovo Nature Park. Also, collector of *Thaumastocephalus* specimens in Velika špilja cave.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY

Basic data	Cave 230 m long, with periodical water flow. Map on Fig. 12.
Microclimate	Ta = 13.3 °C; Ts = 12.2 °C; Tw = 12.4 °C; RH: 96-100%; CO ₂ = 2960 ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	Gastropoda: <i>Paladilhiopsis pretneri</i> Bole & Velkovrh, 1987.
Other taxa in LT	Amphipoda: <i>Niphargus</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp., <i>Biokoviella</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Stalagtia</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp.; <i>Troglochthonius</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Heteromurus</i> sp., <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Diplura: <i>Plusiocampa (Stygiocampa)</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Leptomeson</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from Velika špilja cave Šibenik Mt., Dalmatia, HR, located very near NE from Biokovo Mt., the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Velika špilja kod Antunovića (HR2000179), Šibenik Mt., Split-Dalmatia county, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

Thaumastocephalus poggii sp. n. (Figs 13B, 18)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Mosor Mt., Dugopolje, Kotlenice, Špilja Vranjača cave, 450 masl, 26.03.2003, leg. R. Ozimec. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106608.

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE. Body (TL 2.00 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.36 mm, HW 0.27 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.69 mm) long; scape 0.15/0.05; pedicel 0.08/0.04; antennomere III 0.05/0.03, IV 0.04/0.03, V 0.04/0.03, VI 0.04/0.03, VII 0.03/0.04, VIII 0.03/0.04, IX 0.03/0.03, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.15/0.09. Pronotum (PL 0.37 mm, PW 0.37 mm)

Fig. 11. *Thaumastocephalus inesae* sp. n. in Velika špilja cave, on 02.07.2022, photo R. Ozimec.

Fig. 12. Velika špilja cave, vertical and horizontal profile (after Jalžić et al., 2010).

Fig. 13. Aedeagi, dorsal view. **A:** *Thaumastocephalus inesaе* sp. n.; **B:** *Thaumastocephalus poggii* sp. n.; **C:** *Thaumastocephalus roglici* sp. n.; **D:** *Thaumastocephalus visianii* sp. n. Scale bar 0.1 mm.

as long as wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.51 mm, EW 66 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.39/0.65 mm. Profemora with minute proximal thorn. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine minute. Aedeagus (Fig. 11B) 0.41 mm long, left paramere more robust than right one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with one robust and two slender asymmetrical sclerites.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus poggii* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the right paramere more robust than left one, slightly constricted sub-basally, without subapical process, and with tip subangulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac with one robust and two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora possessing a minute proximal thorn, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a minute median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after our colleague Dr. Roberto Poggi, Genoa, Italy, specialist of Pselaphinae.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY.

Basic data	Big cave, long 365 m, deep -107 m, Map on Fig. 14.
Microclimate	No data
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	LT for 6 taxa: Gastropoda: <i>Troglagopis mosorensis</i> (Kuščer, 1933); Copepoda: <i>Morariopsis kieferi</i> Petkovski, 1959; Isopoda: <i>Oroniscus dalmaticus</i> Strouhal, 1937; Opiliones: <i>Cyphophthalmus noctiphilus</i> (Kratochvíl, 1940); Coleoptera: <i>Haplotropidius taxi taxi</i> (Müller, 1903), <i>Leptomeson dombrowskii</i> (Apfelbeck, 1907).
Other taxa in LT	Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Meta</i> sp., <i>Folkia</i> sp., <i>Stalagtia</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Nelima</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Heteromurus</i> sp., <i>Troglopedetes</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Thaumastocephalus folliculipalpus</i> Poggi, Nonveiller, Colla, Pavićević et Radja, 2001, <i>Laemostenus cavicola</i> (Schaum, 1858), <i>Neotrechus dalmatinus</i> (L. Miller, 1861), <i>Spelaites grabowskii</i> Apfelbeck, 1907; Orthoptera: <i>Troglophilus</i> sp., <i>Dolichopoda</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. So far known only from Špilja Vranjača cave on Mosor Mt., type locality of five other taxa, the last of which was described 65 years ago in 1959. The species can be defined as endemic for Geomorphological monument Vranjača (Nr. 83), Natura 2000 site Mosor (HR2001352), Mosor Mt., Split-Dalmatia county, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

Fig. 14. Špilja Vranjača cave, vertical and horizontal profile (after Jalžić et al., 2022).

Thaumastocephalus roglici sp. n. (Figs 13C, 15, 18, 19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Samogorska špilja cave, 717 masl, 25.05.2004, leg. H. Bilandžija. Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106609.

PARATYPES: 1 male, Biokovo Mt., Župa, Gradska špilja cave, 746 masl, 21.06.2007, leg. H. Cvitanović; 1 male, same data as previous, but collected in 25.05.2004, leg. B. Jalžić; 1 male same data as previous but collected in 08.05.2012, leg. J. Bedek; 2 males, same data as previous but collected in 15.11.2010, leg. P. Rade;

1 male, same data as previous but collected in 21.06.2007, leg. P. Rade; 1 male, Biokovo Mt., Župa, Matijaševa peć cave, 584 masl, 15.11.2011, leg. R. Ozimec; 1 male, same data as previous but collected in 25.06.2004, leg. B. Jalžić (Coll. ROC, CDP, MHNG).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE.

Body (TL 2.00 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.40mm, HW 0.32 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.72 mm) long; scape 0.15/0.05; pedicel 0.08/0.04; antennomere III 0.04/0.03, IV 0.03/0.02, V 0.03/0.02, VI 0.03/0.02, VII 0.03/0.02, VIII 0.03/0.02, IX 0.04/0.03, X 0.04/0.04, XI 0.15/0.08. Pronotum (PL 0.37 mm, PW 0.38 mm) slightly longer than wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.54 mm, EW 65 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.39/0.65 mm. Profemora with proximal thorn. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median spine absent, or forming at most a low swelling. Aedeagus (Fig. 11C) 0.48 mm long, left paramere more robust than right one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with three slender asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. 1.92-2.00 mm.

Fig. 15. *Thaumastocephalus roglici* sp. n. in Gradska špilja cave on 15.11.2011, photo by R. Ozimec.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus roglici* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the left paramere more robust than right one, slightly constricted sub-basally, without subapical process, and with tip subangulate; 2) the aedeagal internal sac with three slender sclerites; 3) the profemora possessing a minute proximal thorn, and 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a minute median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after the academician, geomorphologist Josip Roglić (1906-1987), who carried out geomorphological researches on the Biokovo Mt.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY.

Basic data	Small cave, 24 m long, -7 m deep, Map on Fig. 16.
Microclimate	Ta = 3.4-7.1 °C; Ts = 4.5-6.6 °C; Tw = - °C; RH: 96-100%; CO ₂ = - ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglotic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	No.
Other taxa in all 3 caves	Gastropoda: <i>Semilimax</i> sp., <i>Spelaeoconcha</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp., <i>Armadillidium</i> sp., <i>Oroniscus</i> sp., <i>Trichoniscus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp., <i>Macrochaetosoma</i> sp., <i>Apfelbeckia</i> sp.; Acari: <i>Rhagidia</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Sulcia</i> sp., <i>Stalagtia</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Cyphophthalmus</i> sp., <i>Nelima</i> sp.; Palpigradi: <i>Eukoeningenia</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp., <i>Neobisium</i> sp.; Scorpiones: <i>Euscorpius</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Bilobella</i> sp., <i>Heteromurus</i> sp., <i>Orchesella</i> sp., <i>Tomocerus</i> sp., <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Zygentoma: <i>Coletinia</i> sp., ; Coleoptera: <i>Tychobythinus</i> sp., <i>Neotrechus</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp.; Orthoptera: <i>Dolichopoda araneiformis</i> Burmeister, 1838, <i>Gryllomorpha</i> sp., <i>Troglophilus</i> sp.; Lepidoptera: <i>Triphosa</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. So far known from 3 caves: Samogorska, Gradska and Matijaševa. The species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

Fig. 16. Samogorska špilja cave, vertical and horizontal profile.

Thaumastocephalus visianii sp. n. (Figs 13D, 17-19)

HOLOTYPE: male, Croatia, Dalmatia, Biokovo Mt., Župa, Bošak jama pit, 739 masl, 17.11.2005, leg. R. Ozimec; Coll. ROC, Inv. Nr. GMV 106610.

PARATYPES: 1 male, same data as holotype; 1 male, same data as previous but collected on 04.04.2006, leg. H. Cvitanović (Coll. CDP;MHNG).

DESCRIPTION OF HOLOTYPE.

Body (TL 2.24 mm) shiny, reddish-brown, smooth, covered with dense setae becoming much longer on posterior part of elytra, and sparser on abdomen; legs, antennae and maxillary palpi concolor. Head (HL 0.44 mm, HW 0.34 mm) longer than wide, distinctly narrower than pronotum, eyeless. Antennae (AL 0.77 mm) long; scape 0.20/0.06; pedicel 0.08/0.05; antennomere III 0.05/0.02, IV 0.03/0.02, V 0.0/0.03, VI 0.03/0.02, VII 0.04/0.02, VIII 0.04/0.02, IX 0.04/0.04, X 0.05/0.05, XI 0.18/0.08. Pronotum (PL 0.43 mm, PW 0.42 mm) slightly longer than wide, barrel-shaped. Elytra together wider than long (EL 0.60 mm, EW 72 mm). Abdomen slightly wider than elytra; first visible tergite 0.40/0.69 mm. Profemora slightly thickened sub-basally. Protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half; median

spine obtuse. Aedeagus (Fig. 11D) 0.45 mm long, right paramere more robust than left one, both with four preapical setae; internal sac with one robust and two slender asymmetrical sclerites.

VARIABILITY. TL 2.23 – 2.24mm.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS. *Thaumastocephalus visianii* sp. n. can be distinguished from its congeners by: 1) the right paramere more robust than left one, broadly constricted in middle, without subapical process, with tip acutely angulate; 3) the aedeagal internal sac possessing one robust and two slender sclerites; 3) the profemora slightly thickened sub-basally, without a proximal thorn; an 4) the protibiae shallowly depressed in distal half, possessing a median spine.

ETYMOLOGY. The species is named after Roberto de Visiani (1800-1878), famous botanist born in Šibenik, Dalmatia.

HABITAT AND ECOLOGY.

Basic data	Small pit deep -18 m, long 10 m, simple morphology.
Microclimate	Ta = 7.4 °C; Ts = 7.3 °C; Tw = - °C; RH: 100%; CO ₂ = - ppm
Basic habitats	Natura 2000: 8310; NKS H.1.1.4. Caves and cave systems with troglolitic invertebrates.
LT for taxa	No
Other taxa in LT	Gastropoda: <i>Spelaeoconcha</i> sp.; Isopoda: <i>Alpioniscus</i> sp.; Chilopoda: <i>Lithobius</i> sp.; Diplopoda: <i>Biokoviella</i> sp., <i>Brachydesmus</i> sp.; Araneae: <i>Sulcia</i> sp., <i>Lepthyphantes</i> sp., <i>Typhlonyphia</i> sp.; Opiliones: <i>Nelima</i> sp., <i>Cyphophthalmus</i> sp.; Palpigradi: <i>Eukoenia</i> sp.; Pseudoscorpiones: <i>Chthonius</i> sp.; Collembola: <i>Pseudosinella</i> sp., <i>Verhoeffiella</i> sp.; Coleoptera: <i>Laemostenus</i> sp., <i>Neotrechus</i> sp., <i>Speonesiotes</i> sp.; Orthoptera: <i>Dolichopoda</i> sp.

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from Bošak jama pit near Lozovci in Župa, the species can be defined as endemic for Natura 2000 site Biokovo (HR5000030), Nature Park Biokovo, Geopark Biokovo-Imotski lakes, Biokovo Mt., Split-Dalmatia County, Croatia, EU and Dinarides. According to the Dinarides biogeographical regions, the species belongs to the Central Dinarides (Dalmatian) endemics (CDE) (Ozimec et al., 2009).

DISCUSSION

Through the past the area of Central Dalmatia was intensively prospected for Coleopteran fauna (Novak, 1952; Nonveiller, 1999, 2006) so it became surprising that nobody found so far representatives of genus *Thaumastocephalus* there. With this 10 newly described species, *Thaumastocephalus* now includes 18 species

Fig. 17. *Thaumastocephalus visianii* sp. n. in Bošak jama pit on 04.04.2006, photo by R. Ozimec.

distributed in Central Dalmatia (17) and Hercegovina (1) (Figs 18, 19). With such distribution (from Kozjak Mt. on NW to Rujnica Mt. on SE) the genus is characteristic for the Middle Dinaric biogeographical region (Ozimec et al., 2009.) We noticed for the first time the sympatric occurrence of *Thaumastocephalus* species in some caves. It was is a case with *T. folliculipalpus* and *T. poggii* sp. n. in the Vranjača cave (Mosor Mt.), and with *T. buljubasici* sp. n. and *T. roglici* sp. n. in Matijaševa peć, Samogorska špilja and Gradska špilja caves (all three grouped above village Župa, on North slopes of Biokovo Mt.).

With no less than 10 species of *Thaumastocephalus* out of 18 occurring on Biokovo Mt. in Central Dalmatia, this mountain clearly appears as the diversity hot spot of the genus (Figs 18, 19), and most likely it's center of origin. From Biokovo Mt. (1762 masl) to the north *T. dahnae* is the most northern species, present on Grabovica Mt. (1066 masl) over Duvanjsko polje field, suggesting that we can also expect some representative of the genus to occur in the vicinity of Imotski region. It is often the case that some species are associated with smaller mountain massifs in the area where the genus *Thaumastocephalus* is present. In NW direction, there are *T. bilandzijae* on Mosor Mt. (1339 masl), and most western species, *T. folliculipalpus*, on Kozjak Mt. (779 masl). In SE direction, on the east of Biokovo

Fig. 18. Distribution of *Thaumastocephalus* species in Central Dalmatia (Croatia). 1. *Thaumastocephalus bartulovici* sp. n.; 2. *Thaumastocephalus basarai* sp. n.; 3. *Thaumastocephalus bilandzije* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 4. *Thaumastocephalus buljubasici* sp. n.; 5. *Thaumastocephalus dahnae* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 6. *Thaumastocephalus dryadalis* sp. n.; 7. *Thaumastocephalus folliculipalpus* Poggi, Nonveiller, Colla, Pavičević & Rađa, 2001; 8. *Thaumastocephalus fortisi* sp. n.; 9. *Thaumastocephalus inesae* sp. n.; 10. *Thaumastocephalus kirini* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 11. *Thaumastocephalus marsici* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 12. *Thaumastocephalus nonveilleri* sp. n.; 13. *Thaumastocephalus poggii* sp. n.; 14. *Thaumastocephalus roglici* sp. n.; 15. *Thaumastocephalus rujnicensis* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 16. *Thaumastocephalus slavkoi* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 17. *Thaumastocephalus troglavi* Hlaváč, Bregović & Jalžić 2019; 18. *Thaumastocephalus visianii* sp. n.

Mt., there are two species, *T. kirini* and *T. rujnicensis* on small Rujnica Mt. (735 masl), on the west strand of Neretva River, suggesting that we can expect further findings of *Thaumastocephalus* on Šibenik Mt. (1310 masl) and Rilić Mt. (1160 masl).

The external morphology of the members of *Thaumastocephalus* is quite uniform. Nevertheless the specimens of this extraordinary troglobitic beetles can be reliably identified by examination of their aedeagi. The aedeagus consist of the basal bulb with diaphragm, and two parameres of unequal length. In some species the left paramere is robust and long, while the right one is weak and short, or the opposite in other species, both parameres possessing three, or four preapical setae. The internal sac possesses asymmetrical sclerites of different appearance, like shorter

Fig. 19. Distribution of *Thaumastocephalus* species on Biokovo Mt.

or longer, broader or narrower rods which are more or less curved or twisted, hook-like or of spiral shape, in pairs or single. We found that the body length of specimens can vary within a population and, therefore, this feature can't be taken as reliable to distinguish species.

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